

United States Department of the Interior

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In Reply Refer to:
2023-0071562-S7

May 8, 2023

Acting North Branch Chief
Attn: L. Kasey Sirkin
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Subject: Formal Consultation on the Napa County Stream Maintenance Program in Napa County, California and Appending to the *Programmatic Biological Opinion for Issuance of Permits under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act, including Authorizations Under 22 Nationwide Permits, for Projects that May Affect the Threatened California Red-Legged Frog in Nine San Francisco Bay Area Counties, California* (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers [Corps] file number 2019-00081)

Dear Acting North Branch Chief:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) February 25, 2022, request for initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Napa County Stream Maintenance Program (SMP) in Napa County, California. Your request was received by the Service on September 14, 2021. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally threatened Delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*), federally endangered Ridgway's rail (formerly known as California clapper rail) (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*), endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*), federally threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered Clara Hunt's milk-vetch (*Astragalus clarianus*), endangered Keck's checkerbloom (*Sidalcea keckii*), endangered Sebastopol meadowfoam (*Limnanthes vinculans*), and endangered soft bird's-beak (*Cordylanthus mollis ssp. mollis*). No critical habitat for these species is present in the project area.

This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402). The federal action on which we are consulting is the issuance of a Clean Water Act Section 404 permit to the Napa County Flood Control and Water Conservation District (District) to issue a five-year Regional General Permit (RGP) for flood control channel maintenance activities in flood control channels and creeks, including the Napa River and its tributaries. Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), the Corps submitted a

biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. From these findings, the Corps concludes that the SMP may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog. The Corps also concludes that the SMP may affect, and is not likely to adversely affect the Delta smelt, California clapper rail, California least tern, western snowy plover, salt-marsh harvest mouse, Clara Hunt's milk-vetch, Keck's checkerbloom, Sebastopol meadowfoam, and endangered soft bird's-beak or their habitats.

The Corps requested that the proposed project be appended to the June 18, 2014, and reauthorized on October 3, 2019, *Programmatic Biological Opinion for Issuance of Permits under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act, including Authorizations Under 22 Nationwide Permits, for Projects that May Affect the Threatened California Red-Legged Frog in Nine San Francisco Bay Area Counties, California* (Programmatic Biological Opinion) (Service file number 08ESMF00-2014-F-0389, Service 2014). The Service has determined that the proposed project meets the suitability criteria of, and is within the geographic area analyzed in, the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Therefore, this letter is an agreement by the Service to append the proposed project to the Programmatic Biological Opinion and represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California red-legged frog. By appending the proposed project to the Programmatic Biological Opinion, Napa County Flood Control and Water Conservation District acknowledges and accepts all of the conservation measures outlined within the Programmatic Biological Opinion, including, but not limited to, the measures to minimize adverse effects. Napa County Flood Control and Water Conservation District will also follow all reasonable and prudent measures, and all terms and conditions as directed by the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The Corps will ensure that Napa County Flood Control and Water Conservation District meets all of these obligations.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following:

- 1) The January 2019 Biological Assessment;
- 2) The Corps' February 25, 2022 initiation letter;
- 3) Phone calls and emails between the County of Napa, the Corps, and the Service; and
- 4) Other information available to the Service.

The Service agrees with your determination that the proposed action is not likely to adversely affect the the Delta smelt, California clapper rail, California least tern, western snowy plover, salt marsh harvest mouse, Clara Hunt's milk-vetch, Keck's checkerbloom, Sebastopol meadowfoam, and soft bird's-beak.

Our concurrence that the SMP is not likely to adversely affect the Delta smelt is based on the following factors:

- These species occur in downstream, tidal portions of the Napa River, however occurrences within the lower Napa River are considered rare.
- Program activities in the tidal portion of the action area are limited. Maintenance of the Napa Flood Protection Project, located adjacent to the tidal portion of Napa Creek, includes minimal work in the wetted portion of the channel. Minor low-impact activities

such as maintenance of flapgates within the wetted portion of the tidal reach may occur, but grading or other larger activities are not anticipated.

- Proposed project Best Management Practices (BMPs) and herbicide formulations used by the SMP would reduce the potential impacts on Delta smelt.
- If dewatering is required in tidal portions of the action area such as for maintenance of flapgates, installations of fish exclusion barriers would occur at low tide, when the work area is dry or has little water.

Our concurrence that the SMP is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail is based on the following factors:

- This species generally inhabits coastal salt or brackish marshes and are known to occur in the brackish marsh habitat in southern Napa County. An occurrence overlaps the 45-acre mitigation site adjacent to the Edgerly Island facility, and a small portion of the Edgerly Island facility. Habitat within the mitigation site is marginal for this species, consisting of mainly pickleweed and ice plant, with very little tidal mudflat area.
- Program activities within the mitigation site such as channel maintenance and vegetation management could potentially impact nesting California clapper rail, through increased human presence if they were to nest in this area. Activities such as disking at the Edgerly Island Facility could result in temporary increased noise. This noise would be limited in duration and is not anticipated to interfere with California clapper rail nesting.
- Implementation of BMP BIO-1: *Minimize Impacts to Nesting Birds via Site Assessments and Avoidance Measures* would reduce the potential for adverse impacts to California clapper rail. This BMP includes pre-maintenance site inspections during the nesting season (February 15- August 15). If nesting birds are found, a buffer will be established around the nest and maintained until the young have fledged. California clapper rail are known to occur south of American Canyon, in Solano County. Maintenance areas in American Canyon are not anticipated to provide suitable habitat for California clapper rail.
- In addition to BMP BIO-1, several other BMPs would avoid or minimize impacts to California clapper rail and their habitat. These measures include:
 - BMP GEN-1: Work Windows. This measure would minimize the potential for impacts during the nesting season.
 - BMP GEN-2: Minimize the Area of Disturbance. This measure would minimize the area of impact to habitat.
 - BMPs RESTOR-2 (Seeding) and RESTOR-3 (Planting Material). These measures would restore bird habitat that is temporarily disturbed by maintenance activities. With implementation of BMPs, any impacts to California clapper rail would be insignificant. No indirect effects to this species are anticipated.

Our concurrence that the Maintenance Program is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern and Western snowy plover is based on the following factors:

- Suitable nesting habitat for these species is not present within the proposed Program Area. Known nesting areas for California least tern and Western snowy plover are located a minimum of 0.1 mile away from the proposed Program Area. Program activities at the Edgerly Island Facility, and the adjacent mitigation site would generate temporary noise, but due to the distance of known occurrences of this species from the action area, noise is not anticipated to exceed ambient conditions in areas that could potentially support

California least tern and Western snowy plover breeding. No indirect effects are anticipated.

Our concurrence that the Maintenance Program is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse is based on the following factors:

- Occurrences of salt marsh harvest mouse are documented in the vicinity of the action area in salt marshes of southern Napa County. An occurrence overlaps the 45-acre mitigation site adjacent to the Edgerly Island Facility (CNDDDB 2018). Suitable habitat for this species is present within portions of the action area containing brackish marsh habitat.
- An occurrence of salt marsh harvest mouse overlaps the 45-acre mitigation site adjacent to the Edgerly Island Facility. This species may also occur in brackish marsh habitat in the action area, such as in the Napa River/Napa Creek Flood Protection Project Facilities, or at the mouth of drainages in American Canyon. Program activities in the 45-acre mitigation site are limited, and typically include hand removal of invasive species, minor channel excavation with hand tools to maintain hydraulic connectivity and opening/maintaining the sluice gates to allow for tidal flushing of channels. These activities are not anticipated to result in direct impacts to salt marsh harvest mouse. These activities may result in indirect beneficial effects on salt marsh harvest mouse, by maintaining suitable habitat for this species.
- Program activities in the Napa River/Napa Creek Flood Protection Project Facilities do not occur in suitable habitat for this species. Herbicide application to control perennial pepperweed, within the Napa River/Napa Creek Flood Protection Project area may occur adjacent to suitable habitat for salt marsh harvest mouse. Implementation of BMP BIO-3: *Protection of Sensitive Fauna Species from Herbicide Use* and BIO-6: *Avoid and Minimize Impacts to Special-Status Plant Species and Sensitive Natural Vegetation Communities* would reduce potential adverse effects on salt marsh harvest mouse and its habitat to a level that would be insignificant. Program activities in American Canyon drainages are also not anticipated to occur in suitable habitat for this species. Noise generated by Program activities in areas adjacent to salt marsh habitat are anticipated to have insignificant effects on salt marsh harvest mouse.
- The District will prepare an annual report documenting maintenance activities conducted in the prior year within salt marsh harvest mouse habitat, which occurs within the Floodplain and Marshplain terrace areas. The annual maintenance report is submitted to the Service by March 30 and describes the dates and types of maintenance activities conducted, extent of work (by quantity and location), quantity of pickleweed habitat removed, salt marsh harvest mouse sightings, and photographs.

Our concurrence that the Maintenance Program is not likely to adversely affect the Clara Hunt's milk-vetch, Ketch's checkerbloom, Sebastopol meadowfoam are based on the following factors:

- It is the District's intent to avoid all impacts to listed plant species, to the greatest extent feasible. Standard operating procedures for Program activities include implementing BMP BIO-4: *Avoid and Minimize Impacts to Special-Status Plant Species and Sensitive Natural Vegetation Communities*. This measure includes pre-maintenance planning by a qualified botanist to identify maintenance sites with the potential to support special status plant species listed in Appendix C. This pre-maintenance planning would also include targeted plant surveys, as needed, to ensure that species are not present in work areas.
- If a listed plant species is present in a work area and impacts cannot be completely avoided, then the District will contact the Service for guidance.

- The District will not conduct maintenance activities that would result in the reduction of a plant species range or compromise the viability of a local population. The following BMPs would further minimize potential impacts to listed plant species and their habitats:
 - BMP GEN-3 (Minimize the Area of Disturbance), GEN-5 (Staging and Stockpiling of Materials)
 - GEN-6 (Stream Access): These measures would minimize disturbance of special status plants and their potential habitats during construction activities and when constructing temporary stream access routes.
 - BMP RESTOR-2: Seeding: This measure would minimize impacts to special status plant species by stabilizing exposed soils and preventing erosion such that suitable habitat is appropriately restored. Complete descriptions of these BMP are provided in Section 2.4.
 - With implementation of BMP BIO-4, any impacts to listed plants would be insignificant. BMP BIO-4: *Avoid and Minimize Impacts to Special-Status Plant Species and Sensitive Natural Vegetation Communities*. This measure includes pre-maintenance planning by a qualified botanist to identify maintenance sites with the potential to support special status plant species
- No indirect effects are anticipated.

The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California red-legged frog.

Consultation History

- September 9, 2021: County, Corps, and Service staff discussed the possibility of appending the project to the *Programmatic Biological Opinion for Issuance of Permits under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act, including Authorizations Under 22 Nationwide Permits, for Projects that May Affect the Threatened California Red-Legged Frog in Nine San Francisco Bay Area Counties, California* (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers [Corps] file number 2019-00081). Topics discussed included an overview of routine maintenance activities, as well as the area and species impacted by the SMP.
- January 25, 2022: County, Corps, and Service staff participated in an interagency meeting regarding the SMP. Discussion included species determinations and conservation measures.
- February 24, 2022: County, Corps, and Service staff participated in a meeting regarding the project. Discussion included construction schedules, habitat usage, and species determinations.
- February 25, 2022: The Corps officially initiated consultation.
- September 26, 2022: The Corps requested a project update.
- October 5, 2022: The project was re-assigned within the Service.
- October 12, 2022: The Service requested additional conservation measures.
- October 18, 2022: The Corps agreed upon additional conservation measures.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

The purpose of this section 7 consultation is to evaluate the effects of the proposed action on listed species. After reviewing the proposed action with programmatic actions as proposed by the Corps, the Service has determined that the proposed action presents a programmatic action, as defined in 50 CFR § 402.2.

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed action for which incidental take authorization is being requested from the Service is the Corp's issuance of a Clean Water Act Section 404 Regional General Permit to the County authorizing SMP activities within jurisdictional waters. The proposed action therefore includes those components of the County's SMP that necessitate coverage under the RGP, or that are interdependent or interrelated with the 404-permitted activities. The Corps is responsible for enforcing actions carried out in Corps' jurisdictional waters and the Service will enforce all other actions. The following description of the proposed action includes information regarding the SMP's location; a description of its components; and a description of the conservation measure that are incorporated to avoid, minimize, and compensate for effects on federally listed species regulated by the Service.

Project Location

The SMP encompasses areas within Napa County. The majority of the routine maintenance activities will be conducted in the Napa River valley, specifically on tributaries to the Napa River (Figure 1). More detailed maps of the project location are provided in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5. Figure 2 shows the northern portion of the Napa River watershed including key Napa River tributaries Sulpher Creek, Canon Creek, Beard Ditch, and York Creek. Figure 3 depicts the Yountville region including key Napa River tributaries Beard Ditch, Hopper Creek, Yountville Outfall and Collector, Dry Creek, and the Salvador Collector (Solano Ditch). Figure 4 shows the Napa River tributaries maintained in the City of Napa region and Napa County Airport region, including key Napa River tributaries Sheehy and Fagan creeks. Cities within the Project Area which contain District-owned or easement-maintained channels include Calistoga, Napa, St. Helena, and Yountville. Figure 5 shows the Napa River tributaries maintained in the City of American Canyon region including American Canyon Creek, Newell Creek, Walsh Creek, and Rio del Mar. In the southeastern portion of the County, tributaries to Green Valley Creek, which drains to Suisun Bay, are maintained by the District though maintenance in these areas is conducted infrequently. Also shown on the Figure 1 and 3 maps are the restoration projects (Rutherford and Oakville to Oak Knoll reaches), and dredged material rehandling sites (at Edgerly Island and Imola Avenue) maintained by the District.

Figure 1: Napa County SMP Area and Maintenance Reaches

Figure 2: Napa County SMP Calistoga - St. Helena Region

Figure 3: Napa County SMP Rutherford-Yountville-Oak Knoll Region

Figure 4: Napa County SMP Napa Region

Figure 5: Napa County SMP American Canyon Region

Project Activities

Maintenance activities consist of vegetation management including invasive plant management, tree maintenance, and downed tree management; erosion protection and bank stabilization; sediment and debris removal; and small habitat enhancement projects. These core maintenance activities occur mainly in District, County, or City owned engineered flood control channels and in a limited manner in other streams. In addition to these primary activities conducted in District, County or City owned flood control channels, the proposed SMP includes the Napa County Resource Conservation District's (RCD) routine maintenance activities on unpaved roads in upland areas of the County, routine maintenance work at restoration projects along the Napa River, sediment rehandling sites, and flood reduction features of the Flood Protection Project. Although routine maintenance of existing structures and facilities is an on-going activity, the routine maintenance projects identified in the Regional General Permit would occur over the next 5 years.

The proposed Stream Maintenance Program has been developed by the District to provide clear and consistent guidance for the management of streams and channels under the District's authority, including District, County, and other publicly-owned channels, as well as privately owned streams upon request. Additionally, the proposed SMP is also intended to provide a framework for District oversight of the RCD and the Napa County Roads Division in collaborative road maintenance activities. The Stream Maintenance Manual (Manual) (enclosed) provides the organizational framework to oversee routine stream and channel maintenance activities.

Channel Types

The District's operation and maintenance activities occur in five channel ownership types, which are categorized based on the different channel ownership-maintenance arrangements of the SMP. Where the District conducts maintenance, but does not own the channel, then they have maintenance arrangements or easements with other parties to facilitate the maintenance work. The five channel types included in the SMP are described below.

1. **District-Owned Channels / Easements Maintained (Red Channels):** The District maintains 7.3 miles of flood control channels that it owns and for which it has maintenance easements. Many of these District owned channels are engineered channels, typically built by other agencies and deeded to the District. A few of these channels were designed and built to convey a specific design discharge (i.e., the 100-year flood event), but most have no known specific discharge design. Most of these flood control channels were constructed with a trapezoidal cross-section with earthen banks and streambeds. Some channels have sections with hardened banks and beds formed in rock or concrete. Bed and bank hardening typically occurs at or near road and culvert crossings to protect these structures. Typical maintenance activities in District-owned channels include vegetation thinning and pruning, grass mowing on maintenance roads, erosion protection and bank stabilization, sediment and debris removal, trash removal, exotic and invasive vegetation removal, and native tree and shrub planting. Structures and facilities such as access roads, drop inlet culverts, outfalls, flap gates, and road crossing culverts constructed in association with the District's flood control channels may also require routine maintenance. Often, intersecting drainage structures, bridges and adjacent roadways or other infrastructure are owned by an entity other than the District.

2. **County-Owned Channels / Easements Maintained (Green Channels):** These channels (4.2 miles) are owned by Napa County (not the District), but the District performs channel maintenance on them on behalf of the County. Although the District conducts maintenance, it is not obligated to do so, or to maintain any specific level of hydraulic capacity. These channels are generally engineered channels or ditches, but also include some modified streams. County-owned/District-maintained channels include a portion of lower Salvador Creek, Maher-Trent Ditch, Sandra-Kathleen Ditch, and West Pueblo Ditch and Fagan Creek near the Napa County Airport. In general, the level of maintenance and the activities performed on these County-owned creeks is very similar to those described above for District owned red channels. The District surveys these County-owned green channels annually and determines their maintenance needs and priorities in coordination with the County.
3. **Other Public-Owned Channels / Easements Maintained (Purple Channels):** These channels (1.5 miles) are similar to the above, but owned by other public entities such as towns, cities or school districts, for whom the District provides consultations and offers maintenance support upon request. Examples include a section of lower Salvador Creek, portions of the Salvador Creek Tributary, and a small reach of Camille Creek owned by the City of Napa, and Hopper Creek owned by the Town of Yountville (Figure 2-4). The District and the Town of Yountville have established an agreement that allows the District to conduct specific maintenance activities (e.g., sediment management, debris removal, and planting) within Hopper Creek. Maintenance activities, and the survey and maintenance prioritization process described above for District and County owned channels, generally also apply to public owned channels.
4. **Privately-Owned Streams Annually Surveyed for Possible Maintenance (Orange Channels):** Most of Napa County's natural streams are owned by private landowners. The District has identified several flood prone reaches of streams (26 miles), generally within urban areas, where the District surveys conditions to identify potential maintenance needs. If a maintenance need is identified, the property owner is contacted, and permission is requested prior to the District conducting any maintenance. Examples include portions of the Napa River and Sulphur Creek in northern Napa County (Figure 2), Hopper and Dry creeks in the Yountville region (Figure 3), and Browns Valley, Redwood Creek, and some portions of Tulocay Creek in the City of Napa region (Figure 4). The Rutherford and Oakville to Oak Knoll reaches of the Napa River are included in this category (Figure 3). Maintenance activities are generally limited to vegetation and downed tree management, invasive species eradication support, trash removal, and consultations on erosion and bank stabilization. The District's Banks Stabilization Cost Share Program is available to support biotechnical bank repairs (using vegetation) on private property. The District maintains streambanks in the Rutherford and Oakville to Oak Knoll reaches of the Napa River as part of the maintenance agreements for those two restoration projects. The District typically would not conduct sediment removal or hardscaped bank stabilization activities in these privately-owned streams. However, District support is available for such activities if the owner obtains all required regulatory permits.
5. **Other Streams – Maintenance upon Request:** The remaining creeks in Napa County, shown as thin blue lines in the maps of Figures 1 through 5, are privately-owned creeks where District supported maintenance may occur only following a specific owner request for support and District evaluation and confirmation that the request is suitable.

Maintenance work in these channels may typically involve clearing debris or vegetation management to address a flow obstruction or erosion concern. Similar to the privately-owned streams described above, the District's Bank Stabilization Cost Share Program is available to support biotechnical bank repairs on private property.

Dredged Material Rehandling Sites

The District plans to obtain permits for dredge spoil storage operations at the Edgerly Island and Imola Avenue dredged material rehandling sites under a separate process outside of the SMP. In the meantime, the SMP is intended to cover ongoing maintenance activities at these two sites:

1. **Edgerly Island:** The Edgerly Island dredged material rehandling site is located approximately 3.5 miles northwest of the City of American Canyon and bordered by the Napa River to the east and Mud Slough to the west (Figure 4). The District purchased the 39-acre property in 1981 for placement of dredged material from the Napa River. The site was modified in 2004 and has capacity to receive approximately 300,000 cubic yards (CY) of material. The District conducts routine disking of the land surface, controls invasive plants, maintains flow gates, and manages ditch drainage on the property. The District also owns the 45-acre parcel adjacent to the west. This site is maintained as a wetland mitigation site. Maintenance activities conducted on the 45-acre parcel are minimal and primarily include maintaining tide gates.
2. **Imola Avenue:** The Imola Avenue dredged material rehandling site is an excavated earthen basin located in the City of Napa on the east bank of the Napa River at the previous location of the Napa Sanitation District's wastewater treatment plant (Figure 4). This site is owned by the District and has the capacity to receive 50,000 CY of material dredged from the Napa River. Maintenance activities conducted on this property include annual disking, mowing the basin levee, and maintaining drainage outfall structures.

Restoration Projects

The following restoration projects are included in the proposed SMP:

1. **Napa River Restoration: Rutherford Reach Maintenance (Dark Blue).** The District, in consultation with the Rutherford Landowner Advisory Committee, proactively protects properties in the Rutherford Reach Benefit Zone Assessment District, and maintains features constructed as part of the Restoration Project that collectively will result in a more stable streambank for the benefit of the property owners. Maintenance activities are identified in the *Rutherford Reach Restoration Maintenance Plan* (refer to SMP Appendix A) and include vegetation management, large woody debris realignment and/or relocation, debris/large trash removal, biotechnical bank stabilization, controlling non-native invasive plants and Pierce's disease host plants, maintaining the function of in-stream habitat enhancement structures, and annual surveys and reporting.
2. **Napa River Restoration: Oakville to Oak Knoll Reach Maintenance (Yellow).** Similar to the Rutherford Reach, the Oakville to Oak Knoll Reach restoration project is maintained by the District. Maintenance is conducted according to the *Napa River Restoration: Oakville to Oak Knoll Reach Community Facilities District Guidance Document* (refer to SMP Appendix A). Annual maintenance activities include monitoring, annual surveys, vegetation management, downed tree and debris

management, and biotechnical bank stabilization projects. Maintenance goals are to minimize bank erosion, maintain functioning of constructed in-stream habitat enhancement structures, and controlling non-native invasive plants and Pierce's disease host plants.

Resource Conservation District Maintenance Projects

The Napa County RCD assists landowners with maintenance of privately-owned unpaved roads throughout the County to prevent impacts on water quality and stream hydrology due to erosion and increased road runoff. Maintenance activities include installing or replacing stream crossings (ford crossings, armored fill crossings, culverts), decommissioning stream crossings, installing cross-road drains (deep water bars), and converting unused roads to recreational trails. The RCD maintains a maximum of 5 miles of roads per year. The District partners with the RCD on rural road maintenance projects and will include these projects in annual reporting.

Napa County Roads Maintenance Activities

The Napa County Public Works Department Roads Division is responsible for conducting routine maintenance within the County at road creek crossings and culverts (Figure 6). The District may partner with the County on road maintenance projects that intersect with streams and will include these projects in the annual SMP reports. Maintenance activities include clearing sediment and debris from concrete lined channels and around structures, vegetation management, herbicide application, downed tree removal, replacement plantings, culvert replacement, biotechnical bank stabilization, and repair or in-kind replacement of drainage structures (e.g., storm drain outfalls, tide gates, sediment basins, trash racks, bridges and access ramps). Biotechnical bank stabilization repair activities are closely coordinated with the District.

Napa River / Napa Creek Flood Protection Project

The District is responsible for maintaining built features of the Flood Protection Project which includes about 6.7 miles of the Napa River and two-thirds of a mile along Napa Creek. The project is intended to reconnect the Napa River to its floodplain, create wetlands throughout the area, maintain fish and wildlife habitat, and retain natural characteristics of the Napa River. Completed project features include creation of marshplain and floodplain terraces; two bypass culverts along Napa Creek; construction of levees, dikes, and floodwalls; biotechnical bank stabilization; two new railroad bridges; utility relocations; maintenance roads; recreational trails; and flood closure gates. Maintenance activities associated with the Flood Protection Project that are consistent with activities currently conducted by the District include clearing debris and obstructions from improved channels and floodways; monitoring and removing sediment; vegetation management and erosion protection on levees, dikes and berms; inspection and maintenance of two underground box culvert bypasses along Napa Creek; and repair of riprap and planted rock slope protection along Napa River and Napa Creek. In addition, storm drainage facilities that require inspection and maintenance under the O&M Manual include drainage channels, flapgates, and storm drainage inlets and outlets.

Figure 6: Napa County Road Department's Maintenance Sites

Specific vegetation management activities include monitoring and replanting vegetation on the marshplain terrace, removing invasive vegetation and debris in the southern portion of the project area (between Imola Avenue and the Highway 29 crossing), maintaining vegetation and turf mats at the dry bypass inlet and outlet, and monitoring grazing activities in the southern portion of the Flood Protection Project. As noted previously, maintenance activities associated with the Flood Protection Project and that are consistent with maintenance activities currently conducted by the District are described in more detail in the Corps approved O&M Manual and thus incorporated by reference in the Manual (Appendix M).

Overview of Maintenance Approach

The SMP includes the following primary activities: vegetation management, including invasive plant management, tree maintenance, and downed tree management; erosion protection and bank stabilization; sediment and debris removal; and small habitat enhancement projects. These core maintenance activities occur mainly in the District, Napa County, or City of Napa-owned (i.e., “Other Public Owned”) engineered flood control channels (shown as red, green and purple channels in Figures 1 through 5). Maintenance activities also occur on privately-owned streams throughout Napa County, including the Rutherford and Oakville to Oak Knoll reaches of the Napa River (shown as orange, dark blue and yellow, respectively, in Figures 1 through 5). In addition to these core activities, the SMP also involves other minor maintenance activities and habitat enhancement projects. These maintenance activities are summarized below and described in detail in Chapters 5-12 of the Manual.

Vegetation and Tree Management

Vegetation management generally refers to the trimming, pruning, mowing, and removal of flow-constricting vegetation, or vegetation creating excess instream roughness within the flood control channels and other constructed facilities. Specific maintenance activities presented in the Manual include invasive plant management (Chapter 5), tree and vegetation maintenance (including planting of new trees and shrubs along District-maintained channels) (Chapter 6), and downed tree management (Chapter 7). Vegetation management activities are conducted to maintain flow conveyance capacity, reduce vegetation directed flow that causes bank erosion, establish a canopy of riparian trees, and control invasive vegetation. Management methods typically include hand removal, mechanical removal, and herbicide applications, with heavy equipment used on occasion. Vegetation management and removal activities are relatively consistent from year to year, though locations change depending on recent growth and blockages. Activities are performed year-round in a manner to prevent loss of habitat and erosion, and do not include clear cutting or wholesale removal of vegetation.

Herbicide application for controlling annual herbaceous weeds is conducted during species-specific treatment windows as described in Chapter 4 of the Manual. Maximum monthly average herbicide use is approximately 8 gallons (5 gallons glyphosate and 3 gallons imazapyr) applied over five to eight acres annually. Herbicides may be applied on the banks of channels and on unpaved access roads. In-channel stream bank use of herbicides includes targeted spraying and direct application using a paintbrush on stumps of trees that have been cut during maintenance. While the District does have permit coverage for use of herbicides to control aquatic weeds, no herbicides are applied directly to submerged vegetation in water; herbicides are only applied above the high-water mark within channel banks.

Erosion Protection/Bank Stabilization

The repair and stabilization of stream banks is undertaken when a bank is weakened, unstable, or failing. If left untreated, eroding or failing streambanks can cause damage to adjacent properties; increase the flood hazard and threaten public safety; threaten and impair roads, transportation, and access; generate erosion and increase downstream fine sediment yields; and impact riparian habitat and other natural resources. The District may collaborate with the County Roads Division to repair and stabilize eroding or failing streambanks to address these issues and prevent further degradation of stream conditions.

On average, five to ten bank stabilization projects are conducted annually, with most projects covering approximately 100 to 500 linear feet (lf). Bank repairs involving hardening of engineered channels are limited to 200 lf, whereas repairs of natural channels are limited to 100 lf. Bank stabilization activities for an individual project beyond 1,000 feet are considered beyond routine and outside of the program, which is limited to conducting 2,500 lf of streambank stabilization projects in a given year.

Bank stabilization activities are generally conducted between June 15th and October 31st when streams are at their driest. When possible, bank stabilization is conducted in a preventative manner by planting exposed banks with appropriate native species. If a more engineered approach is needed, biotechnical approaches are preferred. Limited prescriptive biotechnical designs are included in the Manual. More involved projects are subject to individual project permits.

Managed Streambank Retreat. Managed streambank retreat is a passive restoration approach where a landowner removes vineyards within a buffer area along the river channel and installs an alternative agricultural crop that can thrive in a riparian buffer zone or restores the area with native riparian and upland plant species. Within the managed streambank retreat zone, landowners are agreeing to allow the river to naturally expand with the understanding that the District will implement maintenance actions to stabilize the stream bank before it reaches the defined managed retreat line. The District will collaborate with landowners to manage these areas in a manner that meets the riparian enhancement objectives and is consistent with the landowner's land management regime. Typical maintenance actions will include the planting of native riparian and upland species, invasive and Pierce's disease plant management, biotechnical bank stabilization, grading the upper bank to form a stable slope, and erosion control measures.

Currently, landowners within the District's Community Facilities District boundary can participate in the managed bank retreat technique. The overall goal of managed streambank retreat is to create a more expansive riparian corridor along the Napa River and its tributaries to improve conditions for terrestrial species and to better support long-term habitat sustainability. Further discussion of this maintenance concept is provided in Chapter 8 of the Manual, *Streambank Protection and Stabilization*.

Sediment and Debris Removal

Deposited and accumulated excess sediment in District-maintained channels can reduce flow capacity and thereby increase the potential for flooding. Sediment removal activities are focused to target channels whose conveyance capacity is significantly limited due to accumulated sediment and debris. Besides improving flow conveyance for flood management, sediment removal activities may provide other beneficial outcomes including improved fish passage,

improved circulation, and water quality, enhanced geomorphic functions, and improved aquatic habitat. Sediment and debris removal activities are generally conducted from June 15th to October 31st when streams are typically at their driest. The number of sediment removal projects undertaken annually, and the quantity of sediment removed each year depend on recent weather and hydrologic conditions, as well as the frequency and extent of past maintenance activities. The District could implement as many as ten sediment removal projects immediately after a wet winter, and then may go a year or two without needing to conduct any sediment removal projects.

The District typically implements small-scale, localized sediment removal activities in channel segments roughly 250-500 feet long. At sites within the County Roads Division's jurisdiction, localized debris and sediment removal is confined to areas within and around existing culverts and flood control channels (up to 200 CY). On average, 100 to 500 CY of sediment is removed from up to ten sites per year. Most commonly, the District and County Roads Division need to alleviate a specific flow concern at an individual crossing, culvert, or other in-channel facility that experiences moderate sediment accumulation. A sediment removal project may include vegetation management as well, such as when cattails are removed and the District removes sediment accumulation below the cattails in the rooting zone. In general, the District does not undertake large reach-scale sediment removal projects. The Maintenance Program does not include large sediment removal projects that are not routine as described in the Manual.

Sediment and Debris Disposal

Removed sediment and debris is taken to appropriate disposal sites based on the quality and conditions of the collected sediment and debris. Chapter 9 of the Manual describes the program's disposal activities. Sediment and debris removed from District channels is taken to disposal sites maintained in association with the Corps for their dredging activities along the Napa River. These sites are the Edgerly Island Disposal Site and the Napa Sanitation District Imola Site. Sediment and debris may also be taken to the nearest landfill for disposal, as needed.

Other Maintenance Activities

In addition to the primary maintenance activities described above, the District conducts several other maintenance activities as part of the overall Program. Though routine and expected, these other activities occur on a less frequent basis and include replacing culverts, maintaining access roads and drainage ditches, and managing beaver activities. Some of these facilities were constructed under the Napa River/Napa Creek Flood Protection Project (Flood Protection Project).

The frequency and location of minor maintenance projects in a given year varies, depending on past maintenance activities, recent hydrologic conditions, the age of engineered structures, and other factors; however, minor maintenance activities can be conducted anywhere in the District's maintenance jurisdiction. On average, the District anticipates that the SMP will involve between two and three minor maintenance projects per year.

Habitat Protection and Enhancement

The District sees stream maintenance as an integrated stream management approach that involves protecting and enhancing existing instream resources while providing for necessary

flood conveyance capacity in the channel. To this end, the District will implement the following activities as part of the SMP:

Riparian Planting Program. The goal of riparian planting is to enhance habitat for fish, birds, amphibians, and other wildlife using terrestrial riparian areas while providing shading, sources of organic matter and coarse woody debris, and water quality benefits to aquatic species. Opportunities for riparian planting and restoration will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis at all maintenance locations. The planting palette for the Riparian Planting Program is shown in Table 13-2 in Chapter 13 of the Manual. This list of species may evolve as the Program adapts to improve riparian restoration efforts. Riparian planting may also include site preparation, including minor grading and topsoil preparation, and incorporation of soil amendments. Specific revegetation plan details are highly dependent on site-specific conditions at each planting site, particularly with regard to hydrology and soils. Annually, the District plants approximately 590 trees as part of this effort.

Instream Habitat Complexity Features. In coordination with other maintenance activities, District stream managers will evaluate District channels and maintenance sites for opportunities to enhance or develop instream complexity features for mitigation purposes. The goal of these projects is to enhance existing instream complexity features and/or create new features within fish bearing streams in the proposed Project Area. New instream features may be developed to achieve several habitat objectives. The new instream complexity features will be monitored and reported upon in annual monitoring reports. If site appropriate, new instream complexity features can be integrated with gravel augmentation projects. On average, the District anticipates that two instream habitat projects could be implemented per year.

Instream Gravel Augmentation. The general goal of gravel augmentation projects is to improve fish spawning and rearing habitat by enhancing sedimentary materials within the channel bed. The District can reuse watershed specific gravels collected through sediment removal activities as a source for the gravel augmentation projects. When designing a gravel augmentation project, several factors will be considered, including: the existing channel conditions; the grain size distribution of the sediment to be added; the volume of gravel to deposit; the frequency of gravel addition that will be required in light of sediment transport; how the added gravel will interact with to the existing flow regime and/or channel geometry; and the extent of augmentation effects within the channel reach.

Opportunities to augment gravel in non-tidal salmonid streams will be assessed annually. The District will assess stream reaches that are particularly diminished of gravel and assess the feasibility for gravel augmentation. While the number of instream gravel augmentation projects undertaken by the District will vary depending on need and recent hydrologic conditions, the District expects to implement two to five projects annually under the proposed SMP for mitigation purposes.

Activities Not Covered

Activities not covered under the District's routine Stream Maintenance Program include:

1. Capital improvement projects (CIPs);
2. Redesign or reshaping of channels;

3. Maintenance activities that would result in permanent impacts (e.g., bank hardening); and
4. Emergency activities and procedures

A situation is considered an “emergency” if it is a sudden, unexpected occurrence involving a clear and imminent danger that demands immediate action to prevent or mitigate loss of or damage to life, health, property, or essential public services (Public Resource Code Section 21060.3). Although emergency situations will not be covered by the permits authorizing the routine maintenance activities of the SMP, the District will make every effort to follow the guidance provided in the Manual when implementing activities under emergency conditions.

Implementation and Oversight

Annual Work Cycle

Implementation and oversight of the proposed SMP occurs as an annual cycle of activities as shown in Figure 14-1 in Chapter 14 of the Manual, which begins each year with a Program-wide stream reconnaissance and assessment in early spring. The stream assessment then informs the development of that year’s workplan, which is generally developed later in the spring. Project descriptions and impact calculations of maintenance activities and mitigation projects are then developed with additional project planning and refinement occurring in June. The relevant regulatory agencies are notified of the year’s projects in late spring and provided information on project locations, activities, surveys, sediment testing and disposal (if necessary) and any other key issues. Projects are then implemented during the summer season with follow-up annual reporting activities occurring in the fall.

Timing of Work

Maintenance activities primarily occur during the dry season when rain and flows are minimal. Maintenance activities occurring on any creek (excluding Dry Creek, Walsh Creek, and the Napa River) will generally take place between April 15 and October 15. In-channel, ground-disturbing activities on any creek (i.e., tree removal, mechanized vegetation management, bank stabilization and sediment removal) will only be conducted between June 15 and October 31. Similarly, all maintenance activities on Dry Creek, Walsh Creek, and the Napa River will only occur during the June 15 – October 31 work window due to special-status species restrictions. Removal of debris necessary to prevent an imminent flooding threat may occur year-round.

Hand removal activities (i.e., pruning and vegetation removal) may be conducted year-round (except when wheeled or tracked equipment is necessary) in streams that do not support salmonids. In salmonid supporting streams, no vegetation removal would occur beyond December 31 or when the first significant rainfall (i.e., greater than .5 inches), whichever occurs first.

Modification and removal of large wood, such as downed trees, is generally conducted during the dry season unless there is imminent flood danger. Tree removal will not occur between February 1 and August 31 unless a survey is completed to ensure that no nesting birds are present.

Herbicide application will only occur during dry climate conditions, between June 15 and November 15. Extensions may be requested through December 31 or until the first significant rainfall or salmonid migration and spawning begins (whichever occurs first).

Maintenance Methods

The District's approach for maintenance activities is to avoid any unnecessary stream interventions, but to favor hand maintenance over mechanized equipment when such interventions are warranted.

Tree and vegetation maintenance refers to the selective trimming, thinning, and removal of trees and vegetation that increase flood risk or are a flood hazard. Both tree and vegetation maintenance techniques include hand removal using hand-held tools and equipment, mechanical removal using heavier equipment, and herbicide application. The District uses hand-held tools to prune trees and vegetation to maintain flow capacity. At times, impacts to channel banks and stream beds can be minimized through the use of larger equipment for tree removal, including track mowers, winches, rubber-tracked skid steer equipped with a flail mower, or excavators or cranes staged outside the riparian area. Herbicides are generally applied to targeted plants or tree stumps using targeted spot spraying or hand painting of cut stumps. Tree debris from pruning is chipped and either used onsite by landowners for mulching or hauled to the Napa Recycling and Waste Service Center for use and resale by their composting program.

The District conducts the majority of downed tree maintenance using hand tools and equipment. However, on occasion heavy equipment including backhoes rubber-tracked excavators, or cranes may be used to relocate or remove trees within portion of the channel. Additionally, tree rigging techniques are employed to facilitate the re-orienting of downed trees or removal of sections from the channel. Removed trees are chipped for mulch and either left onsite or taken to the Napa Recycling and Waste Service Center for composting.

Bank stabilization repairs would be confined to an area not to exceed 20 feet beyond (landward of) the failed or failing bank or structure, and care will be taken to disturb the least amount of vegetation possible, including mature trees. Bank stabilization activities primarily involve the use of biotechnical methods to stabilize eroding streambanks, which incorporates live vegetation with other natural elements (e.g., wood, biodegradable erosion control products, rock) to provide structural stability to streambanks. Equipment used for bank stabilization activities may include extending arm excavators, small bulldozers (Bobcat style), front-end loaders, and 10 cubic-yard dump trucks. Staging for repair activities will occur on adjacent access roads. Soil and rip-rap will be staged in areas that have been previously disturbed (i.e., service road, turn-outs, etc.). The majority of the work will take place from the top of bank zone and care is taken to minimize the area of disturbance. Overgrown vegetation at bank failure sites will only be removed to the extent necessary to repair the bank.

Equipment used for sediment and debris removal activities range from hand tools for digging out small accumulations of sediment or in sensitive locations to mechanized equipment for larger sediment removal needs. If mechanized sediment removal is necessary, the District prefers using an excavator located outside the channel on access roads. For project areas where using an excavator from the top-of-bank is not possible, sediment removal may be conducted by lowering smaller equipment directly into the channel from a stream crossing. If temporary access ramps are required to lower equipment into the channel, they will be regraded and replanted following the sediment removal activities. In-channel equipment may include a small Bobcat®, skid-steer, or walk-behind power-shovel. A vacuum truck may also be used to remove sediment from smaller culverts and pipes. Sediment removed from the channel is placed in 10- or 20- cubic yard dump trucks (typically parked on the access road adjacent to the channel or within the staging area) and prepared for off-site hauling and disposal.

Detention basins are located throughout the City of American and are intended to improve the quality of urban runoff from impervious surfaces. Routine maintenance of detention basins includes removing dead cattails, bulrush, and other decomposing vegetation where vegetation has visibly clogged outlet pipe openings and removing accumulated sediment. Vegetation and sediment removal work is primarily conducted using hand tools but, depending on the size of the basin, heavier mechanized equipment is used (e.g., backhoes or excavators with a flail mower attached).

Data Management

Data collection and monitoring efforts are critical to measuring the success of program implementation. The District currently maintains an extensive GIS database which includes location and observation data on stream channels managed under their authority. The District also maintains a database for tracking stream maintenance activities that is linked to the District's existing GIS database so that data, such as new species occurrences, are mapped and compared against maintenance activities. To properly track the progress of management activities towards achieving the maintenance program's goals and compliance with permit conditions, these databases are updated or revised as the proposed SMP adapts to best meet the stream maintenance goals.

Data or documentation of the maintenance projects are entered into the database during each cycle of the work plan. The database can be queried to chronicle past maintenance activities or prioritize future actions. The regulatory agencies receive necessary information on maintenance activities (based on the permit requirements and the description of activities in the Manual). Information saved in the database also provides insight into future Manual updates.

Annual Reporting

After the conclusion of each year's maintenance season, the District develops and submits a summary report to the appropriate regulatory agencies by January 31 of the following year. This report includes a summary of the year's maintenance projects describing the workplan status and confirming which projects from the workplan were completed. The report may include additional information on project area conditions, activities employed, the effectiveness of certain activities, possible recommendations for future maintenance, or suggestions to improve the implementation and management of the proposed SMP.

Per the Aquatic Pesticide Application Plan (Appendix G of the Manual), the District must prepare and submit an annual report to the Regional Water Quality Control Board by March 1 documenting whether discharge of herbicides along channel banks, their residues, or their degradation by-products occurred. The annual report contains information including compliance with the *Statewide General NPDES Permit for Residual Aquatic Pesticide Discharges to Waters of the U.S. from Algae and Aquatic Weed Control Applications* (WQO 2013-0002- DWQ; General Permit No. CAG990005), summary of aquatic herbicide application events, summary of monitoring data, and identification of BMPs and their effectiveness in meeting permit requirements.

Reporting Requirements for Napa River/Napa Creek Flood Protection Project

Additional reporting requirements for the Flood Protection Project include:

1. **National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) Annual Report.** The District must submit an annual report to NMFS by April 15 of each year which summarizes the previous year's flood reduction, bank stabilization and revegetation activities. This report describes planned activities for the following year as well as an estimate of all incidental take of steelhead resulting from disturbance, relocation or incidental mortality.
2. **Annual Vegetation and Revegetation Reports.** The District must submit an annual vegetation report to relevant resource agencies and an annual revegetation report to be submitted to the Corps (SPN) District Engineer. The annual vegetation report documents the health of existing vegetation, any observed damage to vegetation, description of naturally recruited native plants, description and quantity of plants to be installed, and photos taken at the time of the inspection. The revegetation report should focus on all revegetation sites and address all significant events that occurred during the prior year, a checklist for all inspections, photographs depicting observed conditions and any identified damage, and a summary of overall vegetation conditions for the reporting period.
3. **Comprehensive Vegetation Monitoring Studies.** For the Flowage Easement Area, the District is required to conduct comprehensive vegetation monitoring studies every 5 years. These studies follow the format and procedures in the Corps study and compare conditions of sites as described in the Project's 1999 Final EIS-EIR and other subsequent documents. Inspections are conducted in the spring between March and May. Vegetation monitoring studies include presence/absence of survey results, an overview of vegetative cover, percent cover of woody species, a visual count of naturally recruited vegetation, and measurements of water salinity along transects.
4. **U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Annual Report.** The District must prepare an annual report documenting maintenance activities conducted in the prior year within salt marsh harvest mouse habitat, which occurs within the Floodplain and Marshplain terrace areas. The annual maintenance report is submitted to Service by March 30 and describes the dates and types of maintenance activities conducted, extent of work (by quantity and location), quantity of pickleweed habitat removed, salt marsh harvest mouse sightings, and photographs.

Five Year Program Review

Every 5 years, the District and the relevant regulatory agencies review the proposed SMP for its overall effectiveness. The District compiles a summary report containing an assessment of maintenance activities conducted to date, BMPs employed, data management, adequacy of adaptive updates and revisions to the Manual, and overall SMP coordination and communication between the District and the regulatory agencies. The 2018 Manual revision process was conducted as part of the 2018 5-year program review process.

Through the 5-year program review process, the District's Program Manager will coordinate discussions and meetings with relevant regulatory agency staff to review the last 5-year program period and discuss any key updates or revisions planned for the next 5-year program period. Manual revisions may also require an updating of permit terms, which occurs through a collaborative process between the District and the relevant permitting agencies.

Programmatic Avoidance and Minimization Measures

The programmatic planning steps taken prior to maintenance work to ensure that activities are conducted effectively and that environmental impacts are avoided and minimized to the greatest extent possible.

Impact and avoidance and minimization are a three-part process where measures are enacted at varying scales and stages of activity implementation. As the initial step, Maintenance Principles provide programmatic guidance to assess if maintenance is necessary, and if necessary, conducted in such a way to reduce impacts. From this basis, more targeted impact avoidance and minimization measures are then applied (second stage) when the annual maintenance workplan is developed, prior to any maintenance work being done, in order to further refine the approach. Finally, the District developed specific channel maintenance best management practices (BMPs) to guide operational activities during maintenance implementation (third stage) to reduce remaining potential environmental impacts. Taken together, these measures provide a comprehensive and integrated approach to avoiding and minimizing SMP impacts.

Environmental Principles

Maintenance Principles were specifically developed to guide the maintenance activities in the Manual conducted by the District. To ensure that environmental impacts are avoided or reduced as much as possible, the following Maintenance Principles are applied:

- Apply the minimum maintenance necessary
- Minimize mechanized maintenance, where possible favor hand maintenance
- Non-routine large-scale maintenance is outside of the proposed SMP
- Understand and monitor the river system and identify hydraulic constrictions/limitations
- Protect and enhance physical processes, landforms, riparian habitat and ecology
- Manage stream resources for long-term sustainability and resiliency

As planning principles, these approaches are used in the development of each year's workplan, prior to any work occurring. When applied, these principles identify the minimum required action and techniques, determine what actions are covered by the SMP, consider river processes, seek restoration and enhancement opportunities, and consider solutions to minimize the ongoing need for repeat maintenance activities at a particular site or reach.

Impact Avoidance and Minimization Measures

The proposed SMP's BMPs in Table 2-1 in the January 2019 Biological Assessment were developed to protect the natural resources of Napa County and the creeks, channels, other facilities maintained by the District. These measures are standard operating procedures designed to be implemented Program-wide to avoid or minimize impacts associated with stream maintenance activities. The BMP's are broken down by proposed SMP activities listed below:

- **General BMPs.** These BMPs will be implemented by the stream maintenance crew, as appropriate and as overseen by site managers, for all activities associated with the

maintenance Program. These BMPs are grouped according to use of general maintenance practices, dewatering activities, public safety, and reporting procedures. The majority of these BMPs are implemented prior to and during maintenance operations, though the level of activity varies depending on the work type.

- **Vegetation Management/Restoration BMPs.** These BMPs provide specific and detailed guidance on the variety of vegetation management procedures implemented by the District. BMPs for the following maintenance techniques are included: tree pruning, plant removal, herbicide application, and site restoration. It is assumed that these measures will be implemented by field crews trained in these procedures. To avoid potential impacts on biological resources, none of these measures will be implemented until authorization from the Stream Maintenance Manager is received.
- **Biological BMPs.** These BMPs will be implemented as appropriate to avoid and minimize impacts on special-status species. These BMPs may be modified during project permitting and agency approvals of annual projects. Additional measures for protection of aquatic species during dewatering activities are described in General BMPs GEN-14 through GEN-16. None of these measures will be implemented until authorization from the Stream Maintenance Manager is received.

Table 2-1 in the biological assessment and Table 4-1 in the Stream Maintenance Manual includes general BMPs applicable to all maintenance activities and project specific BMPs for vegetation maintenance activities, bank stabilization projects, sediment removal activities, post-project restoration, and minor activities. A summary of key avoidance and minimization measures included in the BMP table is provided below.

Work Windows. Channel maintenance activities occurring during the rainy season can result in potential environment impacts, particularly to aquatic habitats. Potential impacts could include erosion from stockpiled sediments or pollutants from work equipment entering the creek. To prevent such wet season impacts, maintenance activities primarily occur during the dry season when rain and flows are minimal. Additionally, regulatory permitting conditions restrict the period and location of certain activities to protect biological resources. Work windows for the maintenance program have been established to protect environmental resources and minimize potential impacts (see Section 2.3.2 *Timing of Work* above). Note these work windows may change as new permits are issued or amended.

Channel Roughness and Capacity Objectives to Guide Maintenance. The District developed a channel roughness and capacity assessment protocol to help guide the annual stream assessment process by identifying which streams require maintenance and prioritizing needed work. The assessment protocol involves a field-based evaluation of conditions. For vegetation management activities, such as tree pruning, this will involve assessing current roughness conditions compared to an allowable roughness criterion for the individual reach. Similarly, the District developed capacity criteria for individual reaches to guide if and when sediment removal activities are necessary.

Biological Surveys. Maintenance activities are conducted in creek channels that provide habitat for a variety of species, including some special-status species which are protected under federal and state regulations. Based on possible occurrence of species as shown in Chapter 3 of the Manual, species specific impact avoidance and minimization measures will be applied when prior to conducting maintenance activities in those reaches.

Aquatic Species Impact Avoidance Approaches. Special-status species including salmonids, California freshwater shrimp, California red-legged frog, and Pacific pond turtles may be present in stream reaches maintained under the SMP. If maintenance activities would disturb habitat of these species, such as maintenance of in-channel vegetation, bank stabilization or sediment removal activities that require channel dewatering, the District would be required to notify and consult with state and federal agencies to obtain their approval of the maintenance activities. The District may establish avoidance, minimization, and mitigation measures with regulatory agencies on a case-by-case basis. If suitable California freshwater shrimp habitat is present, then such habitat will be avoided during implementation of routine maintenance activities.

Herbicide Application Restrictions. All herbicide applications conducted by the District occur in accordance with federal, state, and local regulations. The following measures to avoid and minimize effects of herbicide application are included:

- Herbicides are used on a site-by-site basis and only when necessary, such as when hand and mechanical methods are unsuccessful
- Application will occur when the climate is dry (between June 15 and November 15), wind is not above 5-10 mph, and no rain is in the forecast for the next 24 hours.
- Targeted spot spraying and hand painting of cut stumps are the primary methods of herbicide application. Foliar spraying may be conducted to control growth on larger plants such as exotic trees or large stands of pampas grass.
- District staff and contractors are trained annually on proper herbicide handling and use. Staff are trained by a District or County staff with a current CDPR Qualified Applicator Certificate (QAC). The District contracts all herbicide work out to contractors with QAC and Private Applicator Certification (PAC) on staff.

Contractors and staff with the QAC are required to complete 20 hours of continuing education every 2 years to stay licensed.

Cultural Resource Survey. Most ground-disturbing activities conducted under the SMP (i.e., bank stabilization, sediment removal) must comply with federal, state, and local laws and policies protecting cultural resources and human remains, including but not limited to the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), and Assembly Bill 52. For maintenance activities that require ground-disturbing activities including excavation or repair into soils beyond the channel design (e.g., bank stabilization, culvert replacement), a cultural resources investigation will be conducted by a qualified professional archaeologist and approval from federal and state authorities, as appropriate, prior to performing the maintenance activity. Specific impact avoidance and minimization measures will be applied based on the cultural sensitivity of the project site as indicated in the Cultural Sensitivity Maps (Appendix E) in the SMP Manual. During construction, the District will retain a qualified archaeologist to be present onsite during any ground disturbing activities within highly sensitive cultural areas, and a cultural resources specialist will evaluate sites involving disturbance/excavation of soil to determine their potential for affecting significant cultural resources.

Pollution Safety Planning. If presence of potential contaminants is observed at the site, the area will be treated as if a hazardous spill occurred. In addition, any observed contamination as evidenced by chemical-like odors, oily sheens, or irregularly colored sediment will be immediately reported to the local fire department's hazardous materials team. Soil testing may be conducted prior to sediment removal and bank stabilization projects. Should soils be encountered during maintenance that contain concentrations of listed substances that exceed hazardous waste levels, the contaminated area will be treated as if a hazardous spill occurred (i.e., a Spill Prevention and Response Plan will be implemented) and all measures to ensure compliance with federal, state, and local regulations will be taken.

Public Outreach. To reduce potential inconvenience to the public and protect their safety during maintenance activities, measures such as keeping the work site clean, reducing loud noises, and maintaining vehicle and pedestrian access will be implemented. Work will be limited to normal business hours (8:00 a.m.–5:00 p.m.) and routine activities in residential areas will not occur on Saturdays, Sundays, or County holidays. Sound control devices will be actively used on all power equipment, and prior notification of work will be issued to all adjacent properties within 180 ft. of a project location where heavy equipment will be used. The District may conduct an annual presentation of general maintenance activities to the public for informational purposes.

Additional Conservation Measures as agreed upon by the Service and Corps shall be implemented:

Inspect On-site Material Left Overnight. Because amphibians are attracted to cavity-like structures such as pipes and may seek refuge under construction equipment or debris, amphibians may become trapped or injured if such materials are moved. All construction pipes, culverts, or similar structures, construction equipment or construction debris left overnight within 100 feet of the project area shall be inspected for listed species prior to the beginning of each day's activities. If a listed species is discovered, handling or relocating of the animal shall be conducted by a Service-approved biologist.

Inspect and Cover Open Excavations. Open excavations greater than 2 feet deep will be completely covered at the end of each workday to prevent wildlife entrapment. All trenches and excavations will be inspected for wildlife each morning and prior to backfill. If an excavation cannot be completely covered, an escape ramp must be provided. If a listed species is observed, the listed animal will not be handled, and the Service will be contacted immediately for guidance. All entrapped animals will be removed only by a Service-approved biologist.

Action Area

The action area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action." To account for Program-related noise and potential minor turbidity generation, the action area is defined as a 100-foot buffer from maintenance areas. The District's operation and maintenance activities occur in five channel ownership types, district-owned channels, county-owned channels, other public-owned channels, privately-owned streams, and 'other' streams.

For the purposes of this consultation, the Corps has defined the scope of analysis to include all maintenance areas, in addition to a 100-foot buffer around these areas to account for Program-related noise and potential minor disturbances. Direct effects of the Program may include temporary elevated noise levels from equipment, disturbance to the substrate from maintenance

activities, and vehicles during maintenance activities, and temporary visual modifications or distractions. Construction-related noise is considered to have the largest potential zone of influence of these direct effects. If water is present during maintenance activities, other direct effects may include temporary increases in turbidity near the work areas. Generation of turbidity would be temporary and localized.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the action area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which determines all consequences to listed species that are caused by the proposed federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-federal activities in the action area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the listed species.

Status of the Species

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ rangewide status, please refer to the *California Red-legged Frog (Rana draytonii) 5-Year Review: Summary and Evaluation* (Service 2022, https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/4025.pdf). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since the December 2022 5-year review was finalized, with habitat loss and fragmentation, isolation of populations south of Santa Barbara County and in the Sierra Nevada, invasive predators, and climate change being the most significant effects. While there have been continued losses of California red-legged frog habitat throughout the various recovery units described in the species Recovery Plan (Service 2002), including the South and East San Francisco Bay unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion of jeopardy for the species.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the action area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the action area, the

anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the action area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the environmental baseline.

The proposed project locations occur within a mixture of aquatic and terrestrial habitats. Aquatic environments include streams and drainages, freshwater wetlands, and brackish wetlands. Terrestrial habitats include riparian woodlands, oak woodlands, and non-native annual grasslands.

Aquatic habitats in Napa County (County) are highly diverse in size, type, and function. The streams that form the drainage network within the County are the primary aquatic habitat relevant to program activities. To a lesser extent, freshwater wetlands, including seeps and springs, may also be affected by program activities. Except for a brackish wetland adjacent to the Edgerly Island Facility, the brackish wetland within the Flood Protection Project area, and some brackish wetlands in the downstream portions of maintenance areas in the vicinity of American Canyon, saline wetlands that occur in the southern part of the County are not included in the Program Area. The District also conducts maintenance in the Edgerly Island vicinity and maintains a 45-acre wetland mitigation site adjacent to the dredged material rehandling facility. RCDs road maintenance activities will likely occur in or near tributary streams generally higher in the watershed than other proposed Program activities, affecting habitats such as intermittent streams.

Streams and drainages in the Program Area include tributaries to the Napa River, San Pablo Bay, Suisun Creek, Putah Creek and Green Valley Creek, and other smaller water conveyance features such as ditches and swales. The characteristics of the aquatic habitat associated with these features vary considerably. Several of the Napa River tributaries provide perennial aquatic habitat for fish and wildlife. Many smaller streams and drainages experience periods of low flow or no surface flow during summer and fall. Only a few species of vascular plants typically grow within fast-flowing streams. Species that may be found in or adjacent to such streams in the proposed Program Area include torrent sedge, giant chain fern, spicebush, and small-fruited bulrush. Certain non-vascular plants, such as aquatic mosses and filamentous algae that are tightly attached to rocks by strong holdfasts, can survive the fast current. Low gradient, slow flowing streams and drainages in the proposed Program Area support dense growth of aquatic vegetation such as *Ludwigia*, water plantain, and smartweeds. Common, widespread bird species that use stream habitats in the proposed Program Area include herons, egrets, and waterfowl. Some species of amphibians use stream habitats for breeding, particularly bullfrogs, which are not native to California. Native amphibians that may be present in and around aquatic habitats in the proposed Program Area include Coast Range newt, Pacific treefrog, California red-legged frog, foothill yellow-legged frog, and California toads. Pacific pond turtles also use these habitats, often concentrated in areas of optimal habitat such as side channel and backwater areas. Functions and values provided by instream aquatic habitat include the following: Maintenance of surface and groundwater quality through filtration and decomposition of pollutants; Groundwater aquifer recharge; Water for human, animal, and wildlife use; Wildlife habitat; and Opportunities for conservation and restoration of fish and wildlife habitat. Listed species with the potential to be present in streams and drainages include steelhead, California red-legged frog, and California freshwater shrimp may potentially occur in streams and drainages in the action area. California freshwater shrimp are found in pools in low-gradient streams such as the Napa River, Garnett Creek and Huichica Creek (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Delta smelt, longfin smelt, and

green sturgeon may potentially occur in downstream, tidal portions of streams in the action area, such as the Napa River.

Freshwater wetlands are distributed throughout the proposed Program Area in swales, low-lying areas and around ponds and reservoirs. Freshwater wetlands in the Program Area are typically characterized by monocots— grasses and grass-like plants in the sedge and rush families—that are tolerant of extended exposure to saturated soils or inundation by surface water. Perennial wetlands that hold water for most or all of the year are characterized by dense stands of cattail and bulrush or tule. Ponds and other open water areas may support plants with floating leaves, such as pondweeds, mosquito fern, and duckweed, or submerged plants, such as Canadian pondweed and *Najas* spp. Associated species in perennial wetlands include other bulrush species, creeping spikerush, mannagrass, floating water-primrose, water-plantain, umbrella flatsedge, mint, buttercup, and smartweeds. Wetlands with more seasonal water supply support sedges and rushes. Mediterranean barley, Italian ryegrass, curly dock, and hyssop loosestrife are common associated species in seasonal wetlands. Freshwater wetlands, particularly those with native vegetation and high structural complexity, provide high-quality wildlife habitat that offers nesting, foraging, roosting, and cover for a variety of species. The high plant productivity typical of freshwater wetlands offers abundant food sources and cover for wildlife. The wildlife community that receives the most evident benefit from freshwater wetlands is birds. Common and uncommon bird species typically associated with emergent freshwater wetlands that may be found in the County include grebes, rails (e.g., Virginia rail, American coot), herons, egrets, ducks (e.g., wood duck, cinnamon teal), shorebirds, marsh wren, and common yellowthroat. In addition to the abundance of birds, other vertebrates found in freshwater wetlands include amphibians, reptiles, and mammals. Amphibians and reptiles that use freshwater wetlands include Pacific chorus frogs, western toads, and garter snakes, which in turn provide food for animals including birds and mammals. Mammal visitors to freshwater wetlands include deer mouse, California meadow vole, river otter, and mule deer. Muskrats and beaver may use freshwater wetlands for cover, food, and/or hut construction. Many bat species forage for insect prey over wetlands. Freshwater wetlands typically contain many invertebrates—such as dragonflies, craneflies, and snails—that provide an important food source for other species. Functions and values provided by freshwater wetlands include the following: Maintenance of surface water quality through filtration and decomposition of pollutants; Groundwater recharge; Flood control, due to storage of flood and storm surge waters; Water for stock and wildlife use; Wildlife habitat; and Recreation, including bird watching, hunting, and fishing. Maintenance of native communities, connectivity with the watershed, and a natural hydrologic regime are necessary to maintain these values. Aquatic habitats and wetlands are frequently colonized by invasive species of plants, invertebrates, fish, and amphibians. Invasive species readily displace native species and commonly prey upon them. Ponds, reservoirs, canals, and lowland rivers are often the sites of exotic or nonnative species introductions and concentrations, including many aquatic invertebrates (e.g., insects, snails, clams, crayfish,), many nonnative fish species, and bullfrogs (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). In general, alteration of hydrology and environmental change resulting from dams, water withdrawals, and land use conversion of riparian and floodplain areas are the primary threats to streams in the proposed Program Area. Altered hydrology has been identified as the primary cause or a contributing factor in the decline of several fish species (Moyle et al. 1996), and low summer flows in Napa River tributary streams have been shown to reduce feeding and growth opportunities for rearing steelhead (Stillwater Sciences 2007). Listed species with the potential to be present in freshwater wetlands include California red-legged frog and Sebastopol meadowfoam.

Brackish wetlands in the proposed Program Area include the 45-ac mitigation site adjacent to the Edgerly Island Facility, the diked tidal marsh on the Edgerly Island facility, and brackish emergent wetlands in the Flood Protection Project area. Vegetation in the mitigation site is dominated by ruderal species in the ecotone between wetland areas and upland area, with some pockets of native plants such as coyotebrush. Wetter areas of the site include species such as pickleweed and various hydrophytic graminoids. Based on communication with the Corps and because the Edgerly Island wetlands are within an isolated and enclosed basin controlled by a structure, the wetlands were found to not be federally jurisdictional under the Clean Water Act.

Vegetation community composition in the diked brackish marsh on the Edgerly Island site generally follows the topographic gradients. The lowest vegetated portions of the site are dominated by saltmarsh sandspurry; and non-native brassbuttons is also present. As elevation increases the diked marsh community includes nonnative species such as fat hen and rabbitsfoot grass. The upper extents of the diked marsh habitat are dominated by perennial ryegrass and salt grass. Dominant plant species in brackish emergent wetlands in the Napa River Flood Protection Project include southern bulrush, saltmarsh bulrush, Oregon gumweed, marsh jaumea, rushes, narrowleaved cattail, pickleweed, and salt grass (Stillwater Sciences 2018). Tidal mudflats are found adjacent to brackish wetlands in the Flood Protection Project area, and vegetative cover is sparse in these areas (Stillwater Sciences 2018). Small areas of brackish wetlands may also be found in the downstream portion of maintained channels in the vicinity of American Canyon.

Brackish wetlands provide habitat for many species. Bird species typically associated with brackish wetlands include similar assemblages to those associated with freshwater wetlands. Mammals such as shrews, bats, raccoons, and mice may occur in this habitat. Listed species such as salt marsh harvest mouse, California clapper rail, and soft salty bird's-beak may occur in these habitats. Riparian woodlands and forests are found along waterways throughout the County. Valley oak riparian woodlands and mixed willow riparian forest are the most common riparian vegetation community types in the Napa Valley, Carneros, and Jameson/American Canyon areas (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Valley oak riparian woodlands in Napa County are characterized by valley oak and one of two suites of co-dominant tree species, either California bay, coast live oak, walnut and Oregon ash, or Fremont cottonwood, and coast live oak (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Valley oak riparian woodlands constitute only a small fraction of the County's overall area but are particularly valuable in terms of providing wildlife habitat. Valley oak riparian woodlands that are not heavily grazed typically contain a variety of plant species in the understory, such as bracken fern, Santa Barbara sedge, arroyo willow, California rose, common snowberry, California blackberry, and wild grape (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Valley oak woodland and savanna also occurs on the open valley floor, where it was historically quite extensive (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005, SFEI 2008). Mixed willow riparian woodlands and scrub includes Pacific willow, red willow, black willow, narrowleaf or sandbar willow, and arroyo willow (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). These species may be found in pure or mixed stands. Other species found in mixed willow riparian forests include Fremont cottonwood, valley oak, coast live oak, California rose, California blackberry, common snowberry, white alder, and big-leaf maple.

Riparian woodlands and forests are valuable for wildlife since they provide shade, water, favorable microclimates, and important movement corridors. In-stream woody debris from riparian trees and shrubs also provides important habitat elements, forming scour pools and logjams used by insects, amphibians, and fish (Riparian Habitat Joint Venture 2004). Riparian forests are particularly important for California land bird species, providing breeding habitat, over-wintering grounds, migration stopover areas (Riparian Habitat Joint Venture 2004), and

movement corridors for bird species with somewhat limited mobility such as California quail. Multilayered, structurally complex vegetation enhances quality of riparian habitat. Wildlife associated with riparian forests include amphibians such as Pacific tree frog; reptiles such as ring-necked snake and sharp-tailed snake; birds such as black phoebe, yellow-breasted chat, bushtit, Pacific-slope flycatcher, and orange-crowned warbler; and mammals such as raccoon, ringtail, bobcat, and shrews. In recent years beavers have established a colony on Salvador Creek near Vintners High School. A variety of bat species may roost in riparian trees including the western red bat, a state species of special concern. Riparian habitat also contributes essential functions to aquatic habitats that support steelhead, Chinook salmon, and other fish species. Functions and values provided by riparian woodlands and forest include the following: Stabilization of stream banks; Maintenance of stream water temperatures through shading of the channel; Movement corridors for wildlife; Habitat for wildlife, and inputs of coarse woody debris and detritus to streams. Listed species that may occur in riparian woodlands include valley elderberry longhorn beetle and Sebastopol meadowfoam.

Oak woodlands are common in the County, covering more than 167,000 acres or 33 percent of land in the County (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Most of these woodlands are mixed oak with multiple dominant oak species such as coast live oak, interior live oak, blue oak, and California black oak (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Other oak woodlands include evergreen oak woodlands (dominated by coast live oak and interior live oak) and deciduous oak woodlands (dominated by blue oak or valley oak) (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). The understory in these woodlands often contains annual or perennial grass species, poison oak, hairy honeysuckle, and rigid hedge nettle (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Oak woodlands provide valuable food resources and habitat for wildlife. Acorns and oak-feeding insects provide food for many bird and wildlife species (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Birds such as ash throated flycatcher, Hutton's vireo, orange-crowned warbler, lark sparrow, Bullock's oriole, Lawrence's goldfinch and lesser goldfinch are found in oak woodlands (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Mammals which may be found in these habitats include northern raccoon, striped skunk, gray fox, bobcat, Columbian black-tailed deer, and mountain lion (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Oak woodlands provide habitat for wildlife; listed species that may occur in oak woodlands include northern spotted owl, Clara Hunt's milk-vetch, and Keck's checkermallow.

Annual grassland covers approximate 10 percent of the County (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Dominant species in this habitat include non-native annuals such as wild oat, brome, wild barley, Italian ryegrass, medusa head and annual fescue (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Forbs which may be present include miniature lupine, Douglas's lupine, California poppy, clover, filaree, birdsfoot trefoil, evening snow, purple owl's-clover, valley tassels, blow wives, buttercup, star thistle, and smooth cat's-ear (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Many wildlife species use grasslands for breeding or other habitat. Bird species known to breed in annual grasslands include western bluebird, loggerhead shrike, California horned lark, Savannah sparrow, Say's phoebe and western meadowlark (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Species such as golden eagle, northern harrier, American kestrel, white-tailed kite, and red-tailed hawk use annual grasslands as foraging habitat (Jones & Stokes and EDAW 2005). Non-native annual grasslands provide habitat for wildlife; listed species that may occur in non-native annual grasslands include Keck's checkermallow.

California Red-legged Frog

Six occurrences of California red-legged frogs have been documented within the County (CDFW 2018). Three occurrences are located in the vicinity of American Canyon. Of the remaining

occurrences, two are in the southern portion of the Putah Creek drainage, and one occurrence is located to the south of Pope Valley. California red-legged frogs may be present in suitable habitat within the proposed Program Area.

Critical habitat for California red-legged frogs within the action area is located in the Putah Creek watershed, where Program activities are limited, and the southern portion of the Napa River watershed.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Direct effects of the proposed Stream Maintenance Program may include temporary elevated noise levels from equipment, disturbance to the substrate from maintenance activities, and vehicles during maintenance activities, and temporary visual modifications or distractions. Construction-related noise is considered to have the largest potential zone of influence of these direct effects. If water is present during maintenance activities, other direct effects may include temporary increases in turbidity near the work areas. Generation of turbidity would be temporary and localized.

RCDs road maintenance activities will likely occur in or near tributary streams generally higher in the watershed than other proposed Program activities, affecting habitats such as intermittent streams.

The action area contains both suitable upland and aquatic breeding habitat for California red-legged frog. In most circumstances, maintenance activities, including removal of sediment or large woody debris, bank stabilization, and vegetation management would be implemented in areas that do not support California red-legged frog or, when implemented would utilize appropriate BMP's so as to not adversely affect California red-legged frog and their habitat. However, in limited circumstances, completion of maintenance in areas where activities could potentially result in adverse effects on California red-legged frog and their habitat could be determined to be necessary to alleviate flooding or safety concerns. Maintenance activities in these limited circumstances could directly impact individuals or reduce habitat quality by removing breeding substrate and escape cover. The District's standard operating procedures include implementing BMP BIO-7: *Protection of Special-Status Amphibian and Reptile Species*. This includes pre-maintenance planning by a qualified biologist to identify maintenance sites with the potential to support California red-legged frog. This pre-maintenance planning would also include surveys, as needed, to ensure that California red-legged frog are not present in work areas. If California red-legged frog are identified in the work area, several minimization measures are identified to reduce the potential for effects to occur. Implementation of this measure may include capture and relocation of individual California red-legged frog by a qualified biologist (with Service approval), which would be considered take. In addition to BMP BIO-7, implementing several other BMPs would avoid or minimize effects to California red-legged frogs. These measures include:

- BMP GEN-1: *Work Windows*. This measure would minimize the potential for effects during breeding and amphibian egg development.
- BMP GEN-2: *Minimize the Area of Disturbance*. This measure would minimize the area of impact to habitat.
- BMP GEN-3: *Erosion and Sediment Control Measures*. This measure would minimize the potential for siltation due release of fine sediment.
- BMP GEN-7: *In-Channel Minor Sediment Removal*. This measure would minimize disturbance to the potential habitat during sediment removal.
- BMP GEN-10: *Spill Prevention and Response*. This measure would avoid and minimize the potential for degradation of habitat or direct effects due to the release of fuels and lubricants.
- BMP BIO-3: *Protection of Sensitive Fauna Species from Herbicide Use*. This measure would minimize the effects of herbicide on aquatic habitats and fish.

Implementation of these avoidance and minimization measures would reduce proposed Program-related effects to California red-legged frog to a level that would be insignificant in most, but not all circumstances. In limited circumstances, maintenance activities could require relocation of individual California red-legged frogs. Therefore, the potential for stress, injury, or mortality to individual California red-legged frog during relocation activities cannot be completely avoided or minimized. No indirect effects on California red-legged frog are anticipated.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the California red-legged frog, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Napa County Stream Maintenance Program, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Napa County Stream Maintenance Program, as proposed, fits within the parameters of the level of effects analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion and is therefore not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California red-legged frog. We based this determination on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual California red-legged frogs; (2) the habitat disturbance/loss of functionality will be temporary, and disturbed habitat will be restored to pre-project conditions or better; and (3) construction will occur during the dry season which would limit the aquatic habitat being affected by the water diversion and will be outside of the California red-legged frog breeding season.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps or Napa County must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

California Red-legged Frog

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual California red-legged frogs will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of California red-legged frogs that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. The harm and capture of all adult, sub-adult, and juvenile California red-legged frogs within the habitat temporarily disturbed.
2. The injury or mortality of four (4) adult, sub-adult, or juvenile California red-legged frog.

Incidental take of the California red-legged frog has been exempted from a total of 39 miles of aquatic habitat temporarily disturbed in projects appending to the Programmatic Biological Opinion including the proposed project. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the California red-legged frog associated with the Napa

County Stream Maintenance Program will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

The proposed project, as described, fits within the parameters of the level of take analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion, and the Service has determined that this level of take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the California red-legged frog.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California red-legged frog resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed conservation measures. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize incidental take of the California red-legged frog:

- 1) All conservation measures, as described in the biological assessment and restated here in the Description of the Proposed Action section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. The Corps shall include full implementation and adherence to the conservation measures as a condition of any permit or contract issued for the proposed project.
2. If any work will be conducted near or in suitable habitat where California clapper rail and salt-marsh harvest mouse could occur, separate consultation shall be conducted as this may result in adverse effects to those species.

Monitoring:

- a. For those components of the action that will result in habitat degradation or modification whereby incidental take in the form of harm is anticipated, the Corps or the District shall provide a precise accounting of the total acreage of habitat impacted to the Service after completion of construction.
- b. The Corps or the District will immediately contact the Service's Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office (SFWO) at (916) 414-6623 to report direct encounters between listed species and project workers and their equipment whereby incidental take in the form of harassment, harm, injury, or death occurs. If the encounter occurs after normal working hours, the Corps or the District shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day. When injured or killed individuals of the listed species are found, the Corps or the District shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals section below.

- c. For those components of the action that will require the capture and relocation of any listed species, the Corps or the District shall immediately contact the SFWO at (916) 414-6623 to report the action. If capture and relocation need to occur after normal working hours, the Corps or the District shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day.
- d. A post-project completion report shall be provided to the Service documenting with photographs the successful restoration of all habitats temporarily disturbed within the action area and any observations of California red-legged frogs within the action area.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals:

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Coast Bay Division Supervisor of the SFWO at (916) 414-6623.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) The Corps should report sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species to the CNDDDB of the CDFW. A copy of the reporting form and a topographic map clearly marked with the location the animals were observed also should be provided to the Service.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Napa County Stream Maintenance Program. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16(a), reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the federal agency or by the Service where discretionary federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law, and:

- 1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- 2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;

- 3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or written concurrence, or
- 4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Bridget Giblin, Fish and Wildlife Biologist (bridget_giblin@fws.gov) or at (916) 414-6624 or Ryan Olah, Coast Bay Division Supervisor (ryan_olah@fws.gov), at (916) 414-6623.

Sincerely,

Michael Fris
Field Supervisor

Enclosures

cc:

Kasey Sirkin, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, CA
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, CA

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